

The Impact of Hotels E-Service Quality Management on British Tourists' Satisfaction

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Abstract

This paper aims to understand the impact of e-Service Quality Management (e-SQM) in hotels on British tourists' satisfaction. E-SQM and tourist satisfaction are vital concepts that hotels must understand to achieve a competitive advantage. This paper provides a broad-based analysis which will enable to achieve the sustainable competitive advantage in e-tourism industry. Therefore, this research will critically evaluate the crucial dimensions to deliver e-services at desired standard to the tourists. A quantitative approach was used by distributing a questionnaire to British tourists to explore their opinion on the impact of e-SQM on tourists' satisfaction. This paper applied a descriptive analysis using Cronbach's alpha, mean, standard deviation ANOVA and t-test analysis. The purpose of this paper is to examine and develop a better understanding of relationship between e-SQM in hotels and tourist's satisfaction. The results show that efficiency, privacy/security and reliability have a significant relationship with e-SQM and positively related with tourists' satisfaction

Keywords: e-service quality management, hotels, British tourists, tourists satisfaction

1. Introduction

It is important to explore the distinctive features of e-service quality management in hotels to provide insights for innovative management (Shahin, Pool, & Poormostafa, 2014). One reason for the poor quality of e-service levels across hotels is managers tend to solve e-service marketing problems with techniques that are for tangible products (Abukhalifeh, 2015). It happens because of inadequate understanding about the nature of e-services (Uddin, 2015). Therefore, this research will investigate hotels e-SQM dimensions needed for British tourists' satisfaction.

Technology-based interfaces have developed many changes in ways of providing services to tourists in hotels (Chow, 2017). E-service is more important in hotels strategies for their e-commerce activities (Hahn, Sparks, Wilkins, & Jin, 2017). Online services are different from traditional services. E-service could be supposed as a sort of interactive information. This information can be used by hotels to analyse tourists' behaviour to customize the e-service (Law, Qi, & Buhalis, 2010).

E-services can be divided into three categories: core services, additional services, and problem-solving services (Ma Sabiote, Ma Frías, & Castañeda, 2012). There are three steps in e-service experience: interaction, transaction and fulfilment (Murphy & Tan, 2003). There are other definitions for electronic services in hotels. (Shahin, Pool, & Poormostafa, 2014) illustrate three components in e-service: interactivity, transaction and fulfilment. (Murphy & Tan, 2003) claimed that the following elements can influence tourist's satisfaction regarding hotel web experience such as: usability, interactivity, content and reliability.

(Abebe Tessera, Alisa Hussain, & Ahmad, 2016) identified a model for e-service experience in hotels which consists of individual differences, e-service convenience, e-service satisfaction, intention, and e-service quality. (Eraqi, 2006) believes that the importance of e-services in hotels is not only for understanding whether the electronic commerce is successful or not, but also it creates experience for tourists to have the interaction with the hotels. This information easily can be taken from tourists and analysed for the customization. (Cotîrlea, 2011) defines e-service quality as a tourist interaction with hotel website in all phases: "the extent to which a website facilitates efficient and effective booking, purchasing, and delivery.

Sustaining quality in e-service need complex operations in terms of e-service design, e-service delivery and marketing activities (Wafik, 2016). Therefore, there are two types of internet interaction in hotels: between tourists and hotel's employees and the interaction between tourists and hotels website. Most of the interaction between employees and tourists has been replaced with tourist-websites interaction (Ma Sabiote, Ma Frías, & Castañeda, 2012). Thus, tourist-websites interaction is considered as a source of e-service quality and will be investigated in this research.

2. Literature review

2.1 Defining e-service quality

E-service in hotels consists of all steps of purchase such as gathering information, initiation, sale execution and after-sale supports which are performed electronically (Yoon, 2011). Many researchers like (Parasuraman, Zeithaml, & Berry, 1998) and (Coleman, Xiao, Bair, & Chollett, 1997) believed that quality in services act as an important key to reach loyalty and satisfaction.

(Javadi & Jamalipour, 2011) developed 21 items to measure the e-service quality and they lead to five final dimensions which are: trust, web site interface, access, credibility and attention. (Brady, Cronin, & Brand, 2002) discuss points that are related to electronic service quality which indicates that e-service quality will affect the tourist's satisfaction and have effects on purchase process and decision making. According to (Parasuraman, Zeithaml, & Berry, 1998), hotel managers should understand how tourists would evaluate and perceive e-service.

(Uddin, 2015) defined the quality of a e-service as the total composite e-service characteristics of marketing, engineering, manufacture, and maintenance through which the product and e-service in use will meet the expectations of the tourist. The main component of the quality definitions is to understand tourist expectations and needs (Stockdale, 2007).

Service quality can be defined as the totality of features and characteristics of a product or services that bear on its ability to satisfy stated or implied needs (Sigala & Sakellaridis, 2004). E-service quality as "the differences between tourist expectations and perceptions of e-service (Shahin, Pool, & Poormostafa, 2014). The hotel e-service quality is difficult to define, because it depends on both the e-service outcome and on e-service delivery (Murphy & Tan, 2003).

2.2 Perceptions and dimensions of e-service quality in hotels

The hospitality managers should manage the e-service quality in an effective way (Ma Sabiote, Ma Frías, & Castañeda, 2012). Delivering quality to tourists and meeting their expectations is very critical (Lee, Barker, & Kandampully, 2003). Therefore, theoretical knowledge on the perceptions and dimensions of e-service quality is very important to understand tourist e-service experience (Law, Qi, & Buhalis, 2010).

It is very critical to understand how tourists perceive hospitality services and how they evaluate whether they have experienced e-service quality (Lacle, 2013). Guests perceive hospitality services in terms of e-service quality and how satisfied they are with their experiences (Kim, Chung, & Lee, 2011). Hospitality establishments recognise that they can compete more effectively by having a competitive advantage with respect to e-service quality and improved tourist satisfaction (Javadi & Jamalipour, 2011). As shown in Figure 1, e-service quality reflects the tourists' perception of reliability, assurance, responsiveness, empathy and tangibles. Satisfaction is influenced by perceptions of e-service quality, price, personal factors and situational factors (Bateson, & Hoffman, 1999).

Figure 1: Perceptions of e-service quality and tourist satisfaction
Adapted from: (Bateson, & Hoffman, 1999)

(El Saghier, 2015; Wafik, 2016; Chow, 2017; Hahn, Sparks, Wilkins, & Jin, 2017) explain the dimensions of e-service quality in details as follows:

- Reliability has been consistently shown to be the most important dimension of perceptions of e-service quality. Reliability is defined as the ability to perform the promised e-service dependably and accurately. In its broadest sense, reliability means that the hotel delivers on its promises - promises about delivery, e-service provision, problem resolution and pricing.
- Responsiveness is how to help tourists and to provide accurate e-service. This dimension highlights prompt responds in dealing with tourist requests and problems.
- Assurance is defined as employees' knowledge and courtesy and the ability of the firm and its employees to inspire trust and confidence. This dimension is likely to be particularly important for services that tourists perceive as high risk or for services of which they feel uncertain about their ability to evaluate outcomes.
- Empathy is defined as the caring, individualised attention that the firm provides its tourists. Tourists want to feel understood by and important to firms that provide e-service to them.

According to (Brady, Cronin, & Brand, 2002), satisfaction or dissatisfaction is a response to tourists' perceived discrepancy between prior expectations and performance. When tourists are satisfied, it will give a big drive to make purchases. (Abebe Tessler, Alisa Hussain, & Ahmad, 2016) distinguished between e-service quality and tourist satisfaction, e-service quality is part of the cognitive process, whereas tourist satisfaction is part of the affective process.

(Yoon, 2011) suggests that the quality of the e-service has a very close relationship with tourist satisfaction as e-service quality can create tourist satisfaction. In a study conducted by (Kim, Chung, & Lee, 2011) found empirical evidence that the quality of products have a significant effect to tourist satisfaction. There is relation between quality and satisfaction. For example, tourist satisfaction is the positive result on the quality of the services (Bernardo, Marimon, & Alonso-Almeida, 2012).

2.3 E-Service Quality Management (e-SQM)

In the context of the digital economy especially with regard to the new expectations of tourists who demand more personalized services and immediate feedback, e-services are a fundamental tool that hotels must employ to have differentiation from competitors (Abukhalifeh, 2015). Hotels should focus on developing innovative e-services that add a value to tourists (Cofrlea, 2011). The ability of a hotel to be competitive is

to develop customized products through their websites through innovative services (SIGALA & SAKELLARIDIS, 2008).

Tourists in virtual environments tend to buy their travel package with the first supplier that offer innovative e-services (SIGALA & SAKELLARIDIS, 2008). In addition, a loyal tourist often recommends a hotel website to others and these recommendations are important in in the virtual environment (Stockdale, 2007). Tourists want websites that have a simple design, load quickly, and are easy to use (Uddin, 2015). They also demand quality in e-service, on-time delivery, good product presentation, convenience, reasonable prices and clear privacy policies (Parasuraman, Zeithaml, & Berry, 1998). According to (Parasuraman, Zeithaml, & Berry, 1998), e-SERVQUAL scale contains four dimensions: efficiency, reliability, privacy and s and trust. Moreover, The WebQual model, contains four dimensions: ease of use, trust, innovation and communication (Santouridis, Trivellas, & Tsimonis, 2012).

The overall objective of this paper is to analyse the dimensions of e-service quality management in hotels and its impact on British tourists' satisfaction. To address this objective, this research develops the proposed research model (Figure 2) based on the previous literature. Therefore, the relationships between e-service quality dimensions in hotels and tourists' satisfaction will be analysed. This research aims to understand the dimensions of e-service quality management in hotels and its impact on tourists' satisfaction. This research suggests a model which contains five criteria namely: efficiency, privacy/security, reliability, entertainment and communication.

Figure 2: Model of e-SQM in hotels and its impact on tourist's satisfaction

The first dimension of the proposed scale is efficiency. E-service quality management highlights the importance of three aspects of this dimension namely: accurate information on the hotel website, website design and ease of use (Stockdale, 2007). The second dimension of the proposed measurement model is privacy/security. This dimension is consisting of the accuracy of the total price including any additional fees, protection of tourists' personal and banking data. The third dimension of the proposed model is reliability (Chow, 2017). It refers to the maintenance of promises and the provision of the e-service, e-service specifications must meet the tourists' needs and the real e-service contains the same online characteristics offered on the website (Santouridis, Trivellas, & Tsimonis, 2012). The fourth dimension of

the proposed scale is entertainment. This dimension is focusing on the fun and enjoyment while using the hotel website offers. Entertainment as a dimension for measuring e-service quality management is related to the tourists' satisfaction. The last dimension of the proposed scale is communication, which aims to analyse the website's ability to maintain the relationship with tourists when problems arise and its ability to facilitate various ways of communication with tourists (SIGALA & SAKELLARIDIS, 2008).

The main objective of this research is to confirm what are the most important dimensions in measuring e-service quality management in hotels with relation to British tourists' satisfaction, Therefore, several hypotheses have been formulated to achieve the research objectives.

1. Efficiency positively influences the e-service quality management in hotels.
2. Privacy/security positively influences the e-service quality management in hotels.
3. Reliability positively influences the e-service quality management in hotels.
4. Entertainment positively influences the e-service quality management in hotels.
5. Communication positively influences e-service quality management.
6. E-e-service quality management positively influences e-tourists satisfaction.

3. Methodology

The research design for this paper is depending on quantitative approach (Luiz, Costa, Kale, & Werneck, 2003). The study population is consisting of British tourists who booked their trips to Egypt through the official website of hotels. A questionnaire was developed to understand the research phenomenon. A random sample of British tourists were chosen. A questionnaire link was sent to students and staff members of four universities in the UK after having the approval from them to send the questionnaire. The questionnaire was distributed to 1500 tourists. A simple random sampling method is used with a total of 450 tourists were completed the questionnaires with a response rate of 30%. The survey was developed based on a review of literature (Brady, Cronin, & Brand, 2002; El Saghier, 2015; Wafik, 2016; Chow, 2017; Hahn, Sparks, Wilkins, & Jin, 2017). The questionnaire consists of two parts. In the first part, general questions that allow understanding of the sample characteristics such as gender, type of tourist, age and educational level. The second part consists of questions using a Likert scale ranging from 1 "Strongly disagree" to 5 "Strongly agree". The questionnaire focusses on tourists' perceptions of e-SQM and its impact on their satisfaction.

The respondent's answers were analyzed on a five-point Likert scale of 1 to 5 (1 indicates "strongly disagree" and 5 indicates "strongly agree.") to understand the extent of agreement with statements concerning the impact of e-SQM dimensions on tourists satisfaction. The Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) was used for the analysis. Mean and standard deviation analysis were employed to examine the extent of agreement for the respondents' answers. Moreover, t-test and ANOVA analysis were used to test the validity of the research hypotheses and any significant difference between the dependent and independent variables.

In this research, the questionnaire was reviewed by two professors in the field of tourism and hospitality to ensure the validity of the questionnaire. Moreover, the Cronbach Alpha analysis was used to determine the degree of internal consistency of the questionnaire. The goal of reliability analysis is to assure the questionnaire can lead to results that are highly correlated with the results that would be obtained if another test that measures the same phenomena was applied. Table 1 indicates that the Cronbach Alpha achieved high values of .973; .904; .963; .936 .949 and .982. for efficiency, privacy/security, reliability, entertainment, communication and e satisfaction respectively. These values confirms the reliability of the questionnaire.

Table 1. Cronbach Alpha for Initial Dimensions

Dimension	Cronbach Alpha
Efficiency	.973
Privacy/Security	.904
Reliability	.963
Entertainment	.936
Communication	.949
E-satisfaction	.982

Analysis

This section illustrates the results achieved through the empirical analysis. As illustrated in table 2, the respondents' profile are mostly male with a percentage of 60.5%. Most of the tourists are coming for leisure 86.3% and their age are between 25-30. Regarding the level of education, most of the respondents are well educated with a bachelor's degree (49.2%)

Table 2: Respondents' characteristics

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Male	272	60,5%
Female	178	39,5%
Total	450	100%
Type of tourists	Frequency	Percentage
Leisure	389	86,5%
Business	61	13,5%
Total	450	100%
Age	Frequency	Percentage
20-30	47	10.5%
31-40	182	40.5%
41-50	117	25.9%
More than 50	104	23.1%
Total	450	100%
Level of education	Frequency	Percentage
High school	205	45.6%
University/ Bachelor	221	49,2%
PhD	24	4,6%
Total	450	100%

On the other hand, tourists' experiences of using hotel websites are illustrated in table 3. Most of the respondents have used the hotel websites for booking (61%) for more than two years.

Table 3. Using hotel websites for booking

Using hotel websites for booking	Frequency	Percentage
Less than 3 months	96	21,4%
3 to 6 months	21	4,6%
6 to 12 months	35	7,7%
More than 12 months	5	11,3%
More than 2 years	293	54,9%
Total	450	100 %

In the case of gender and type of tourist, t-test analysis was used to understand the differences in tourists (Table 4). With regards to the age and the level of education, a comparison of means has been made using the analysis of variance (ANOVA) to analyze the differences in tourists. Regarding the gender variable, Table 3 illustrates that there is a significant difference has been found in the entertainment dimension (0.045). It indicates that males are using the hotel website with more fun than in the case of the females with a significance of .045.

Table 4.T-test analysis according to the gender

Dimension	Variables	Mean	SD	Analysis	
				t-test	Sig
Efficiency	Male	3,81	1,855	,700	,403
	Female	4,02	1,808		
Privacy/Security	Male	3,62	1,955	,023	,879
	Female	3,90	1,983		
Reliability	Male	3,12	1,915	,161	,689
	Female	3,24	1,956		
Entertainment	Male	2,86	1,875	4,034	,045*
	Female	2,78	1,730		
Communication	Male	3,51	1,814	,104	,747
	Female	3,75	1,878		
E-service quality management	Male	3,05	2,100	1,087	,298
	Female	3,40	2,192		
Electronic satisfaction	Male	3,11	2,173	1,253	,264
	Female	3,35	2,267		

* Significance level < 0.05

With regards to tourists' types, there is a difference of means in the dimensions of reliability and entertainment with a significance of .031 and .020 respectively as illustrated in Table 5. These results indicates that leisure tourists are more interested in using hotel websites than business tourists and they are enjoying using those websites.

Table 5.T-test according to the type of tourists

Dimension	Tourist type	Mean	SD	Analysis	
				t-test	Sig
Efficiency	Leisure	3,93	1,840	,048	,827
	Business	3,64	1,813		
Privacy/Security	Leisure	3,75	1,991	,871	,351
	Business	3,57	1,828		
Reliability	Leisure	3,19	1,974	4,697	,031*
	Business	3,04	1,629		
Entertainment	Leisure	2,89	1,857	5,432	,020*
	Business	2,41	1,487		
Communication	Leisure	3,64	1,863	,981	,322
	Business	3,39	1,691		
E-service quality management	Leisure	3,24	2,168	1,425	,233
	Business	2,88	1,945		
Electronic satisfaction	Leisure	3,24	2,236	2,336	,127
	Business				

* Significance level < 0.05.

The ANOVA analysis of tourists ages reveals the significance especially in the entertainment and e-satisfaction dimensions. Table 6 indicates that the more aged tourists, the more significance value for the entertainment dimension (0.047). The Analysis Shows that tourists with age more than 50 are more satisfied with the online services of hotel websites with a significance of (0.018).

Table 6. ANOVA analysis according to the age

Dimension	Tourist Ages	Mean	SD	Analysis	
				F	Sig
Efficiency	20-30	3,89	1,914	1,559	,135
	31-40	4,28	1,850		
	41-50	4,46	1,761		
	More than 50	5,27	1,737		
Privacy/Security	20-30	4,05	2,013	1,836	,069
	31-40	4,28	2,120		
	41-50	3,92	2,397		
	More than 50	5,18	2,040		
Reliability	20-30	3,29	2,180	1,651	,109
	31-40	3,55	2,097		
	41-50	3,77	2,048		
	More than 50	4,73	1,849		
Entertainment	20-30	3,11	1,914	1,982	,047*
	31-40	3,34	1,932		
	41-50	3,46	1,984		
	More than 50	3,82	1,722-		
Communication	20-30	3,71	1,902	1,157	,324
	31-40	3,83	1,853		
	41-50	4,00	2,082		
	More than 50	4,73	1,737		
E-service management quality	20-30	3,55	2,356	1,482	,162
	31-40	3,45	2,197		
	41-50	3,92	2,060		
	More than 50	4,55	1,864		
Electronic satisfaction	20-30	3,53	2,512	2,342	,018*
	31-40	3,97	2,291		
	41-50	3,85	2,375		
	More than 50	4,09	2,166		

* Significance level < 0.05

Table 7 illustrates that all the dimensions are significant especially with the tourists of high school education. The respondents with high school education are the ones who value the design and quality of information of the hotel websites with a mean of 4.03. They are also depending on the security dimension with a mean of 3.89. Moreover, the same results happened with the dimensions of reliability, entertainment, and communication. The results of tourists with high school for the previous three dimensions got the mean of 3.30, 2.81. 3.70 respectively. With regards to the satisfaction, tourists with high school education are the more satisfied with the services offered by hotel websites (3.35).

Table 7. ANOVA analysis according to the age

Dimension	Tourists' education level	Mean	SD	Analysis	
				F	Sig
Efficiency	High school	4,03	1,751	4,327	,002*
	Bachelor	3,81	1,778		
	Master/Doctorate	2,68	1,857		
Privacy/Security	High school	3,89	1,934	4,717	,001*
	Bachelor	3,56	1,897		
	Master/Doctorate	2,58	1,924		
Reliability	High school	3,30	1,884	4,585	,001*
	Bachelor	2,97	1,823		
	Master/Doctorate	2,32	1,887		
Entertainment	High school	2,81	1,752	3,500	,008*
	Bachelor	2,73	1,688		
	Master/Doctorate	2,26	1,910		
Communication	High school	3,70	1,743	5,380	,000*
	Bachelor	3,47	1,788		
	Master/Doctorate	2,53	1,867		
E-e-service quality management	High school	3,31	2,035	4,846	,001*
	Bachelor	2,96	2,040		
	Master/Doctorate	2,47	2,318		
Electronic satisfaction	High school	3,35	2,181	4,699	,001*
	Bachelor	2,97	2,090		
	Master/Doctorate	2,32	2,110		

* Significance level < 0.05

4. Discussion

In this research, the theoretical model used in this analysis is the e-service quality management in hotels and its impact on tourist's satisfaction. This model is the result of the theoretical review of literature. In this model, it has been observed that the correlations between the dimensions of e-service quality management in hotels and tourist's satisfaction are significant mainly with efficiency, privacy/security and reliability, as illustrated in table 8.

Table 8 ANOVA analysis between the dimensions of e-SQM and tourists' satisfaction.

	Efficiency	Privacy/Security	Reliability	Entertainment	Communication	e-SQM
Satisfaction	,001*	,006*	,000**	,777*	,854*	.005*

** Significance level - 0.05

In relation to efficiency, numerous researches have established a direct relationship between this dimension and e-SQM perceived by the tourists (Lee, Barker, & Kandampully, 2003; Abebe Tessera, Alisa Hussain, & Ahmad, 2016; Chow, 2017). Efficiency is one of the most important factors in relation to tourist's satisfaction. This dimension is consisting of content, layout, ease of use and navigation (Cotîrlea, 2011). However, this in agreement with the results of the questionnaire. The results show a positive and significant impact on e-SQM. According to table 8, first hypothesis concerns efficiency has been accepted with a

significance level of 0,001. Although some authors such as (Santouridis, Trivellas, & Tsimonis, 2012) have found that privacy/security does not have a significant impact on perceptions of e-SQM, the analysis of the results revealed that this dimension is significant to tourists satisfaction (0.006). Therefore, second hypothesis concerns privacy/security has accepted. This is in agreement with (Ma Sabiote, Ma Frías, & Castañeda, 2012) when they stated that privacy/security are considered the most important dimension for e-SQM. Furthermore, the obtained results indicate that reliability dimension has a positive relationship with e-SQM and has an impact on tourist's satisfaction with a significance of 0.000. Therefore, the third hypothesis concerns reliability has been accepted. This agrees with the work of (Shahin, Pool, & Poormostafa, 2014) as they stated that reliability dimension is very important for e-customer satisfactions.

On the other hand, the obtained results indicate that the entertainment and communication dimensions are not significant (0.777, 0.845). Therefore, fourth and fifth hypotheses have been rejected. With regards to the relationship between e-SQM and tourists satisfaction, the analysis carried out confirms that the e-SQM has a positive influence on the tourists' satisfaction with a significance of (0.005) Thus, the six hypothesis concerns the impact of e-SQM on tourists' satisfaction has been accepted.

Conclusion

This paper contributions to the concept of e-SQM by identifying the relevant dimensions of tourist's satisfaction. The recognized dimensions of e-SQM applying to the tourist's satisfaction are efficiency, privacy/security, reliability, entertainment and communication. According to the results, it can be concluded that efficiency, privacy/security and reliability are the most important dimensions for tourist's satisfaction. Efficiency and privacy/security of a hotel website are the keys for providing the confidence for the tourists to book a hotel. Moreover, reliability of e-services is important dimension in keeping the loyalty of tourists.

The results revealed that men are more interested in fun during the e-buying process than women. Pleasure tourists place more importance on reliability and entertainment than business tourists. Moreover, the older respondents have interest to entertainment dimension. On the other hand, customers with a high school education consider privacy/security, reliability and communication dimensions more important in e-SQM. It is confirmed that efficiency, privacy/security positively influences the e-SQM. For example, ensuring protection of tourists' data. It can be observed that fulfilling the e-promises have a positive influence on tourists' satisfaction. There is a positive relationship between e-SQM and tourists' satisfaction which might lead to the tourists' loyalty. Therefore, this study recommends that hotel managers should take into their consideration the following dimensions to improve the tourist's satisfaction through e-SQM: reliability, privacy/security and entertainment.

In this study, the proposed model has focused on understand the e-SQM impact on tourists' satisfaction. Therefore, it is advisable to carry out other research that allows an empirical analysis of the developed results with relation to tourists' buying behaviour. Moreover, this research has been applied to a specific sample of British tourists, therefore, future research could address other samples from national or international tourists. Future research could develop deep analysis with relation to individual dimensions of e-SQM. Finally, it will also be beneficial to assess the impact of perceived quality of services in hotels through other means such as social media.

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